

Research

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Cascading carry-over effects of early activity phenotypes in golden eagles

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Early-life conditions are often associated with fitness of animals later in life. Although recent studies show that individual characteristics during development affect the formation of early behavioural phenotypes, we have a limited understanding of the cascade of life-history transitions from early phenotypes to fitness-relevant behaviours in later life stages. Here, we used GPS and body-acceleration data of 35 juvenile golden eagles (*Aquila chrysaetos*) to investigate factors associated with nestling activity levels (overall dynamic body acceleration; ODBA), the relationship between nestling activity and the timing of fledging and post-fledging activity, as well as the effects of post-fledging activity on post-fledging movements and the timing of dispersal. We found that brood size, but no other intrinsic or extrinsic factors, was associated with activity levels. Active nestlings fledged earlier and remained more active after fledging than passive nestlings. Increased post-fledging activity levels were related to an increased number of pre-dispersal forays and an early timing of dispersal. Even though some effects showed reduced certainty, our results provide evidence for downstream effects of behavioural differences expressed in the nest. They suggest that early activity phenotypes of nestlings drive the timing of subsequent life-history transitions, thereby representing a key mechanism that links behavioural phenotypes in early life with future performance.

1. Introduction

During ontogeny, most organisms transition between life stages during which they are confronted with often fundamentally different environments [1]. Because of the challenges associated with new environments, early-life stages are characterized by high mortality, typically occurring just after transitioning from one life stage to another [2]. Survival during these periods can be affected by intrinsic factors, such as genetic make-up or sex [3], but it is frequently shaped by early-life conditions [4,5]. For instance, food availability, climatic and weather conditions, and social interactions have all been shown to affect early-life survival [6,7]. Beyond their immediate impact on survival, early-life conditions can also drive the expression and development of individual traits that subsequently carry over to later life stages [8]. Such carry-over effects of early-life conditions can have crucial consequences on stage-specific individual performance, affecting population composition and persistence [9,10]. In the last few decades, research has provided fundamental insights into the prevalent associations between early-life conditions and fitness outcomes later in life [8,11]. However, such within-individual associations often considered only two points, early and late in the ontogenetic trajectory, thus overlooking the processes by which early-life conditions are translated across multiple life stages (but see [2,12]).

The mechanisms underlying carry-over effects of early-life conditions can be linked to physiological characteristics such as oxidative stress, corticosterone levels or telomere length [13,14]. However, early-life conditions can also shape behavioural phenotypes, i.e. individual behavioural characteristics, which then may be associated with future fitness [15]. Thereby, we are becoming increasingly aware of natal effects that affect future locomotor and cognitive abilities [16], but also social traits [17]. While behavioural phenotypes are based on intrinsic factors, they are strongly modulated by the conditions experienced [17]. Yet we still have a limited understanding of the downstream effects of early behavioural differences over multiple life stages.

In altricial birds, fledging from the nest is one of the most critical life-history transitions, as it marks the first step towards independence from parental care and initiating flight through an unfamiliar environment [18]. Growth, physiology and behaviours related to flight start to develop in the nest, and key developmental thresholds—such as adequate feather and muscle growth—must be reached for successful fledging [19,20]. Consequently, conditions during the nestling period, including food availability, weather and social interactions between siblings within the nest, were found to affect body condition and the timing of fledging [6,21–23]. Recent findings further suggest that these early conditions can also shape behavioural phenotypes [17]. These individual behavioural differences may finally mediate the cascading effects from nest environments to individual differences in post-fledging behaviour and fitness.

For territorial species with extended parental care, becoming independent and leaving the parental home range after the post-fledging period (i.e. the start of natal dispersal) represents another fundamental life-history transition [24]. In many species, an early start to dispersal can facilitate its outcome by enabling early detection and monopolization of resources, floater areas and breeding sites ([24] but see [25,26]). Yet, individuals need to reach behavioural maturity to be successful [20]. Individual development is often not terminated at fledging but continues into the post-fledging period [19,20,27]. Beyond morphological and physiological developments, birds need to improve behavioural skills such as locomotion or vigilance [20,28]. As in the nestling period, developmental trajectories during the post-fledging period are expected to affect the timing of subsequent life-history transitions such as the departure to dispersal [29]. The post-fledging development is likely to be shaped by both behavioural differences carried over from the nestling period and conditions experienced during the post-fledging period. While our understanding of the environmental factors affecting the timing of dispersal is increasing [30,31], the effects of behavioural differences on dispersal timing are not well established. This restricts our mechanistic understanding of early life effects on individual fitness components later in life and possible consequences for populations.

Behavioural differences are difficult to record for free-roaming species during the post-fledging period. However, animal-borne accelerometers now allow quantifying individual behaviours. For example, overall dynamic body acceleration (ODBA) [32] has been shown to be a reliable proxy for activity-related energy expenditure [33]. ODBA can thus be used to quantify individual differences and developmental trajectories of time investment into energy-demanding behaviours such as locomotor training in the nest or flight behaviours after fledging [12,33]. Thereby, accelerometers allow

investigating carry-over effects of early-life activity levels to activity levels in subsequent life stages [12] and enable novel mechanistic insights into how early-life differences shape survival, recruitment success and distribution of behavioural phenotypes after independence.

Here, we investigate individual activity levels of nestlings as well as their carry-over effects over two major life-history transitions (fledging and departure to dispersal) in an Alpine population of golden eagles (*Aquila chrysaetos*). The Alpine golden eagle is a large territorial, non-migratory raptor that breeds in high-mountainous habitats [34]. Golden eagles largely rely on environmental energy for energy-efficient soaring flight [35]. After fledging, golden eagles show an extensive post-fledging period where they improve flight proficiency [27,36,37], with large individual variation in the timing of permanent departure from the parental territories [28,29]. First, we quantified the effects of potential factors driving individual activity levels in the nest, including sex and body condition (intrinsic), social nest environment (presence of a sibling) and characteristics of the nest surroundings. Second, we investigated the correlation between activity in the nest and the timing of fledging, expecting that high activity levels would result in early fledging. Third, we quantified the correlation between nestling activity levels and post-fledging activity levels, expecting that high activity levels in the nest translate into high activity levels after fledging. Finally, assuming that post-fledging activity levels reflect the development of flight behaviours [27], we analysed the effect of post-fledging activity on post-fledging exploration behaviour and the timing of departure. With this study, we provide novel insights into the behavioural downstream effects of early-life conditions over two life-history transitions, with potentially far-reaching consequences for natal dispersal and recruitment.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study species

The golden eagle (*A. chrysaetos*) is a long-lived, territorial apex predator. With an average territory size of 50 km², golden eagles in the Alps usually rely on multiple nests on cliffs or, less commonly, on trees, which are used alternately for many years [34,35]. Generally, pairs raise one to two chicks per brood, but breeding frequency fluctuates among years and pairs [34]. Chicks fledge at an age of 60 to 85 days between mid-July and mid-August and remain dependent on parental care for multiple months thereafter [28,34,35,38]. During this time, they are mainly raised on fresh meat of Alpine marmot (*Marmota marmota*), chamois (*Rupicapra rupicapra*), ibex (*Capra ibex*), roe deer (*Capreolus capreolus*), mountain hare (*Lepus timidus*) and grouse species (Tetraoninae) but increasingly feed on carcasses of mostly ungulates [34,38]. After departure from their parental territory, juvenile golden eagles spend multiple years in the wandering (transience) phase before trying to take over or establish a territory [25,34,35].

2.2. Study area

The study was carried out in the cross-national Alpine region covering eastern parts of Switzerland (Grisons) and northeastern parts of Italy (Lombardy and South Tyrol). The study area is characterized by a diverse topography of deep valleys and high mountain peaks with steep cliffs [34]. Forests often stretch along valley slopes up to elevations between 1900 and 2300 m, where they give way to open ground and vegetation dominated by grasses and heather. Golden eagle territories almost completely cover the Alpine range, reaching high breeding densities [34].

2.3. Tagging and tracking

Between 2017 and 2020, we equipped 35 juvenile golden eagles (2017: 2, 2018: 8, 2019: 18, 2020: 7) from 27 different territories with solar GSM-GPS-ACC loggers (e-obs GmbH, Munich, Germany), using a leg-loop harness made of two-layered Teflon ribbon with a silicon core (to allow for a relative elasticity of 20%). Tagging took place between late June and mid-July when nestlings were 52.3 ± 4.6 s.d. days old. The age of each nestling was calculated based on the hatching date that was assessed during brood monitoring. The combined weight of transmitters and harnesses of 70 g made up less than 3% of the birds' body mass, as suggested by Kenward [39]. In five territories, two siblings were tagged in the same nest; in two territories, single nestlings were tagged in the same nest but in two consecutive

years, and in one territory, single nestlings were tagged two years apart and in two different nests. In addition to tagging, we ringed, weighed and measured all the nestlings and collected feathers with blood quills for genetic sex identification.

Transmitters recorded GPS and tri-axial accelerometer (ACC) data from 04.00 to 17.00 UTC in summer (May–October) and 09.00 to 16.00 UTC in winter (November–April). These time windows were selected to cover periods of highest golden eagle activity while conserving battery life during low-light conditions. GPS locations were recorded at 20 min intervals. ACC data were recorded every 5 min in 7.9 s bursts, on three orthogonal axes resembling body planes (x , y and z) at a frequency of 33.3 Hz (1188 bytes per burst). The 7.9 s duration was determined from a pilot study evaluating burst lengths, which showed that an approximately 8 s burst captured an optimal amount of behavioural information, and a 0.1 s gap was required to minimize interference with GPS acquisition. All data recorded by the tags were transmitted to and stored in the Movebank database [40]. For subsequent analyses, GPS data were filtered to retain only the first location per hour and to exclude flight speeds exceeding 35 m s^{-1} , thereby standardizing sampling effort across individuals and removing outliers.

2.4. Fledging, exploration and departure to dispersal

We determined the timing of fledging visually by identifying the first trajectory of consecutive GPS locations that clearly departed from the cluster of GPS inaccuracies in the pre-fledging period around the nest. We thus defined fledging time as the first timestamp of the trajectory leading away from the nest site. The age of fledging was then calculated by subtracting the hatching date from the fledging date. To identify explorations and the onset of natal dispersal, we applied a spatio-temporal threshold adapted from ‘method 7’ described in [41]: first, we calculated centroids from a kernel density estimate using the R-package ‘*spatstat*’ [42], based on post-fledging locations clearly prior to emigration. Around each centroid, we defined an 8 km radius to encompass the juveniles’ main home range. This threshold was deliberately selected to slightly overestimate smaller ranges and avoid underestimating large ones, thereby providing a conservative basis for identifying both forays and dispersal movements. Forays during the post-fledging period were defined as movements beyond this 8 km threshold (minimum of one location) for a maximum duration of up to 14 days. This duration was chosen as golden eagles can survive approximately two weeks without feeding (F Schüttelkopf, personal communication). Leaving the parental territory for more than 14 days was thus indicative of independent foraging. The start of each foray was marked by the first location beyond the 8 km threshold, and the end point by the first subsequent location within the threshold. In the case when a bird briefly returned within 6–8 km for less than 2 h, the movement was counted as a single foray rather than two. For each foray, we calculated the duration in days and the maximum linear distance from the juvenile home-range centre in kilometres. For the following statistical analyses, the number of forays was summed, and the average duration of all forays, as well as the mean of all maximum distances, was calculated per individual across the entire post-fledging period. Departure to dispersal was defined as any movement beyond the 8 km threshold without overnight returns for more than 14 days (permanent departure), and the age at departure as the departure date minus the hatching date. Three of the 35 individuals were excluded from the foray and departure analysis as their tags either stopped transmitting ($n = 2$) or they left their parental territory only a few weeks after fledging ($n = 1$) without undertaking any forays.

2.5. Juvenile activity

We used ODBA as a measure of activity [32]. We transformed the raw ACC data into gravitational force g and calculated the mean ODBA for each 7.9 s long ACC burst using the package ‘*moveACC*’ [43]. We determined ODBA during the nestling period for the 11 days prior to fledging and for the first 45 days of the post-fledging period. The 45 days after fledging correspond to the part of the post-fledging period before individuals start undertaking regular and longer forays, and match with the duration of linear activity development [28,29]. We calculated the daily mean ODBA, including recordings from 06.00 to 17.00 UTC. Days with data gaps of more than one full hour ($n = 77$ days from 12 individuals) and days with early forays undertaken within the first 45 days after fledging ($n = 37$ days from 14 individuals) were excluded from the following analyses. For the nestling period (11 days before fledging) and for the early post-fledging period (45 days after fledging), we fitted linear mixed-effects models to investigate the effect of sex and the relative number of days before and after fledging, respectively, on mean daily ODBA (electronic supplementary material, table S1).

The predictor 'day' (i.e. the number of days before or after fledging) was centred and scaled for each period and included as a fixed effect as well as the random slope for each individual. We used the sex-corrected random intercepts derived from these models as indicators for individual ODBA during each period (electronic supplementary material, table S1, figure S1). Additionally, random slopes during the post-fledging period indicated the individual development of daily ODBA over time (electronic supplementary material, table S1, figure S1). By standardizing the predictor 'day' for each period, the random intercepts represented the average ODBA for each period and individual bird.

2.6. Intrinsic, social and environmental variables

As a proxy for an age- and sex-dependent individual body condition, we calculated the deviation of each bird's recorded body mass from the predicted mean body mass at the age at measurement and for the sex of the bird (cf. [44]), i.e. the residual from a linear mixed-effects model with sex (estimate male = -695.68; 95% CrI = -966.55 to -426.46) and tagging age (estimate = 46.64; 95% CrI = -97.76 to 192.31) on body mass as fixed effects while accounting for year as a random effect. To assess the effect of the social environment in the nest, we recorded whether nestlings were singletons or from a brood with two nestlings (binary variable). Nest exposure was measured as compass degrees and translated into northness (degrees) and eastness (degrees) for the analyses. To calculate a proxy for parental habitat quality, we used yearly mean values of the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) per juvenile home range as an indicator for food availability via trophic cascades [45]. To avoid overestimation of used space and foraging grounds, we calculated juvenile home ranges as 90% minimum convex polygons using GPS points within the 8 km threshold defined above. During the post-fledging period, juvenile and parental home ranges are highly similar [46]. As golden eagles mostly forage in open areas that reflect their main prey's preferred habitat [34], closely forested areas were excluded for calculating NDVI (forest type 10 m high resolution layer derived from the Copernicus land monitoring service). We extracted NDVI images using MODIS (moderate resolution imaging spectroradiometer) vegetation indices of the study area taken every 16 days from the beginning of May 2017 to the end of April 2021 at 250 m resolution [47] and cropped them to the extent of each juvenile home range in QGIS 3.18 [48]. We then used the cropped NDVI images to calculate yearly mean NDVI values for each pixel (250 × 250 m), which we subsequently averaged over the entire home range. Negative NDVI values representing unvegetated areas were set to 0.

2.7. Statistical analysis

All statistical analyses were performed using R software v. 4.0.5 [49]. We fitted Bayesian linear mixed-effects models (LMM) and generalized linear mixed-effects models (GLMM) using package '*rstanarm*' [50]. To model nestling activity, we fitted an LMM for ODBA (random intercept of the ODBA model described above) during the nestling period as the response variable and nest exposure, NDVI, body condition, sibling and sex as fixed effects. Likewise, to model post-fledging activity, we fitted an LMM with post-fledging ODBA (random intercept of the ODBA model described above) as the response variable and NDVI, sex, sibling and ODBA in the nest as fixed effects. The fledging age was modelled by fitting an LMM with nestling ODBA, nest exposition, body condition, sibling and sex as fixed effects. Foray patterns were assessed by fitting a Poisson GLMM for the number of forays and LMMs each for mean foray duration (square root-transformed) and mean maximum foray distance (log-transformed) as response variables with post-fledging ODBA, NDVI and sex as fixed effects. Finally, to assess factors influencing the individual age at departure, we fitted an LMM with post-fledging ODBA, NDVI, age at fledging and sex as fixed effects. To account for the non-independence of data between nestlings from the same brood or territory, as well as across years, we included territory, individual ID and year as crossed random effects in all models.

Explanatory variables were checked for collinearity using pair plots and Pearson's correlation coefficient r . Because none of the explanatory variables showed a correlation of $r \geq 0.7$, all were retained in the models. In addition, all continuous explanatory variables were centred and scaled. Models were checked for convergence of the Markov chains with Brooks–Rubin–Gelman diagnostics [51] and for validity using posterior predictive checks (package '*shinystan*'; [52]). Spatial autocorrelation in the residuals was checked using Moran's I (package '*ape*'; [53]) and bubbleplots (package '*sp*'; [54]) and no autocorrelation was detected. Models were created based on ecological hypotheses, and no model selection was performed. Inference and predictions were based on simulated Bayesian

posterior distributions using 10 000 simulations (four chains of 5000 iterations with a burn-in of 2500 each). Additionally, posterior probabilities (PP) were calculated for all model estimates, indicating the probability of both positive and negative estimates to differ from zero. $PP \geq 0.95$ indicated strong support for an existing effect, while $0.95 > PP > 0.9$ indicated a tendency for an existing effect. We assume that the tendencies represent existing effects that show higher uncertainty due to the limited sample size in this study. Therefore, we report tendencies in §3. Unless stated otherwise, model parameters and derived parameters are given as posterior means with 95% CrI.

3. Results

The golden eagle nestlings weighed 3.52 ± 0.53 kg (mean \pm s.d.; range: 2.21 to 4.60 kg; $n = 35$) at tagging. Females weighed 3.87 ± 0.46 kg (range: 2.88 to 4.60 kg; $n = 17$), and males weighed 3.20 ± 0.37 kg (range: 2.21 to 3.70 kg; $n = 19$). Nestling ODBA (daily mean of all 7.9 s bursts) in the 11 days prior to fledging was 0.05 ± 0.01 g (gravitational force; range: 0.03 to 0.08 g; $n = 35$) and increased to a post-fledging ODBA of $0.08g \pm 0.01g$ (range: 0.06g to 0.10g; $n = 32$) in the first 45 days after fledging. Nestlings fledged at an age of 77.9 ± 6.2 days (range: 62 to 90 days; $n = 35$). All individuals undertook multiple forays (mean = 11.9 ± 6.7 forays; range 3 to 29; $n = 32$) during the post-fledging period before departing, lasting for 1.3 ± 1.0 days (range: 0.1 to 4.2 days; $n = 32$) directing them to areas in 22.4 ± 7.4 km (range: 13.3 to 137.2 km; $n = 32$) distance from the parental territory. No juvenile died between fledging and departure from the parental territory. Independence and thus final departure from the parental territory to dispersal occurred at an age of 280.6 ± 40.6 days (range: 185 to 328 days; $n = 32$).

3.1. Nestling period and fledging age

Nestling ODBA was neither associated with the two environmental variables of the nest surrounding, nest exposition and NDVI, nor with sex or body condition at tagging (table 1). Yet, nestlings with a sibling showed higher ODBA than nestlings without a sibling (table 1, figure 1a).

Fledging age was strongly related to nestling ODBA, body condition and nest exposition. Nestlings with high ODBA and better body condition fledged earlier than individuals with low ODBA and poor body condition (table 2, figure 1b). In addition, individuals from southern exposed nests fledged earlier than individuals from northern exposed nests (table 2). Yet, fledging age was not associated with NDVI, sex or having a sibling (table 2).

3.2. Post-fledging period and departure

Females tended to undertake more forays after fledging than males (table 2). Females also spent more time and covered longer distances on individual forays than males (table 2). NDVI affected neither foray behaviour nor age at departure (table 2). All individuals increased ODBA over the first 45 days post-fledging (electronic supplementary material, table S1, figure S1). Males showed higher post-fledging ODBA than females (table 1). Importantly, fledglings with high nestling ODBA also showed high post-fledging ODBA (table 1, figure 2) and high post-fledging ODBA tended to be associated with an increased number of post-fledging forays, but not with the duration and distance of the forays (table 2, figure 3a). Fledglings with high post-fledging ODBA tended to depart at a younger age than fledglings with a low post-fledging ODBA (table 2; figure 3b). When accounting for this ODBA effect, juveniles that fledged later than their peers tended to depart after a shorter post-fledging period than their peers (table 2). This can be explained by the fact that individuals fledging later also fledged later in the season ($r = 0.51$; GLMM: estimate = 0.30; 95% CrI = 0.09 to 0.52), leaving them on average less time until emigration. When propagating the effect of nestling activity to the age of emigration, nestlings with the highest activity emigrated at an 18 days younger age than the nestlings with the lowest activity. Even though sexes differed in fledging age and ODBA patterns both in the nestling and in the post-fledging period, males and females did not differ in age at departure to dispersal (table 2).

4. Discussion

Despite some reduced certainty arising from the relatively small sample size, our findings provide novel insights into the successional carry-over effects extending from the nestling stage through the

Figure 1. (a) Nestling activity (average over 11 days pre-fledging; measured as ODBA in gravitational force g) of golden eagles in relation to having a sibling in the nest (blue) or not (red). Filled squares show means, and lines indicate 95% CrI of model predictions for females with all other model predictors set to their mean values. (b) Age at fledging (in days from hatching) of golden eagle nestlings in relation to nestling activity (average over 11 days pre-fledging; measured as ODBA in gravitational force g). The line shows the mean and shaded areas show 95% CrI of model predictions for females with no sibling, with all other model predictors set to their mean values. Filled circles show raw data points for both sexes. $n = 35$ individuals from 27 territories and 4 years.

Table 1. Estimates of the linear mixed models investigating factors affecting nestling ODBA (11 days pre-fledging) and post-fledging ODBA (45 days post-fledging). Means (estimates), 95% CrI and Bayesian posterior probabilities (PP) are given. Fixed effects with PP ≥ 0.95 are printed in italics. Nestling ODBA: $n = 35$ individuals from 27 territories. Post-fledging ODBA: $n = 32$ individuals from 26 territories. Standard deviations and 95% CrI of random effects are shown in electronic supplementary material, table S2.

model	fixed effects	estimates	95% CrI	PP (< or > 0)
nestling ODBA	intercept	<i>0.052</i>	<i>0.042 to 0.061</i>	<i>1.000</i>
	nest exposure (south)	-0.001	-0.004 to 0.001	0.888
	NDVI	0.001	-0.002 to 0.004	0.766
	sex (male)	0.001	-0.003 to 0.006	0.705
	sibling (yes)	<i>0.006</i>	<i>-0.001 to 0.013</i>	<i>0.963</i>
	body condition	0.001	-0.002 to 0.003	0.741
post-fledging ODBA	intercept	<i>0.077</i>	<i>0.068 to 0.085</i>	<i>1.000</i>
	nestling ODBA	<i>0.005</i>	<i>-0.001 to 0.010</i>	<i>0.959</i>
	NDVI	0.001	-0.003 to 0.004	0.617
	sex (male)	<i>0.006</i>	<i><-0.000 to 0.013</i>	<i>0.967</i>
	sibling (yes)	-0.004	-0.013 to 0.005	0.782

first critical life-history transition of fledging into the post-fledging period, and ultimately influencing the timing of natal dispersal. More active golden eagle nestlings fledged earlier and maintained higher activity levels during the post-fledging period, undertaking more exploratory forays and ultimately departing earlier for natal dispersal than passive nestlings. These differences in activity were partly explained by the social environment in the nest, whereas body condition, sex and the surrounding

Figure 2. Post-fledging activity (over 45 days post-fledging; measured as ODBA in gravitational force g) of juvenile golden eagles in relation to their nestling activity (over 11 days pre-fledging; measured as ODBA in gravitational force g). The line shows the mean, and the shaded area indicates 95% CrI of model predictions for females with no sibling, with all other model predictors set to their mean values. Filled circles represent raw data points for both sexes. $n = 32$ individuals from 26 territories and 4 years.

Table 2. Estimates of the linear mixed models investigating factors affecting age at fledging, exploratory behaviour (number of forays, generalized linear mixed model); foray duration (square root-transformed), foray distance (log-transformed) and age at departure. Means (estimates), 95% CrI and Bayesian posterior probabilities (PP) are given. Fixed effects with $PP \geq 0.95$ are printed in italics; with $0.95 > PP > 0.9$ in bold. Age at fledging: $n = 35$ individuals from 27 territories; forays and age at departure: $n = 32$ individuals from 26 territories. Standard deviations and 95% CrI of random effects are shown in electronic supplementary material, table S2.

model	fixed effects	estimates	95% CrI	PP
age at fledging	intercept	78.281	73.148 to 83.430	1.000
	nestling ODBA	-2.583	-5.121 to -0.058	0.977
	nest exposure (south)	-2.212	-3.712 to -0.688	0.997
	NDVI	-0.148	-1.977 to 1.692	0.566
	sex (male)	-1.796	-5.525 to 1.810	0.838
	sibling (yes)	-0.594	-5.179 to 4.131	0.610
	body condition	-1.509	-3.219 to 0.147	0.962
number of forays	intercept	2.592	1.996 to 3.239	1.000
	post-fledging ODBA	0.191	-0.090 to 0.471	0.919
	NDVI	-0.009	-0.251 to 0.226	0.529
	sex (male)	-0.324	-0.736 to 0.070	0.944
mean foray duration	intercept	1.271	0.987 to 1.587	1.000
	post-fledging ODBA	-0.014	-0.159 to 0.189	0.561
	NDVI	-0.012	-0.150 to 0.176	0.561
	sex (male)	-0.342	-0.645 to -0.059	0.990
mean foray distance	intercept	3.228	3.030 to 3.434	1.000
	post-fledging ODBA	-0.016	-0.138 to 0.102	0.606
	NDVI	-0.006	-0.120 to 0.106	0.538
	sex (male)	-0.313	-0.530 to -0.098	0.998
age at departure	intercept	283.629	257.674 to 311.178	1.000
	post-fledging ODBA	-10.787	-27.874 to 6.191	0.901
	NDVI	-3.180	-20.087 to 14.143	0.656
	sex (male)	-5.923	-32.433 to 20.087	0.687
	age at fledging	-12.150	-28.303 to 4.720	0.926

Figure 3. (a) Number of forays and (b) age at departure to dispersal of juvenile golden eagles in relation to post-fledging activity (over 45 days post-fledging; measured as ODBA in gravitational force g). The line shows the mean, and the shaded area indicates 95% CrI of model predictions for females with all other model predictors set to their mean values. Filled circles show raw data points for both sexes. $n = 32$ individuals from 26 territories and 4 years.

landscape showed no detectable effects. Collectively, our results suggest the emergence of an activity phenotype during the nestling stage that persists across subsequent life stages to affect individual dispersal timing.

4.1. Origin of the activity phenotype

Individual activity, quantified as ODBA, is primarily driven by the frequency of high-motion behaviours [32]. While behaviours such as standing or roosting correspond to activity levels close to basal metabolic rate at rest, behaviours associated with movement, such as flight, result in largely increased activity levels [27,55]. In the nest, behaviour is dominated by low-energy activities, but nestlings increasingly walk, and spread and flap wings as fledging approaches [56]. Arguably, nestlings with siblings may exhibit even greater movement due to social interactions [57]. During the early post-fledging period, birds progressively allocate more time to flight at the expense of roosting [27,28]. Consequently, the birds in our study, showing consistently higher activity levels, probably engaged more frequently in locomotor behaviours, both in the nest and in the early post-fledging period.

Individual differences in activity levels, i.e. the activity phenotype expressed in the nest and in the post-fledging period, can either arise from conditions experienced in the nest [58] or from intrinsic developmental differences in behaviour [59] and tendencies to react to stimuli [60]. The observed effect of sibling presence suggests that the social nest environment can influence activity phenotypes or that parental behaviours affecting activity differ between nests with one and two nestlings. Sibling presence and number are widely known to affect body condition, development and physiology of nestlings, with far-reaching consequences for behaviour and survival later in life [14,17]. However, nestling activity was unrelated to body condition (also when excluding sibling presence from the model: LMM; estimate = 0.001; 95% CrI -0.002 – 0.003) and body condition did not differ between individuals with and without siblings (LMM; estimate = -23.0 ; 95% CrI -345.4 – 298.7), indicating that body condition was not the primary mechanism underlying activity phenotypes. This conclusion held true when using alternative measures of body condition such as scaled mass index [61] (electronic supplementary material, table S3). While sibling presence may have directly increased activity through social interactions [57], the persistence of activity phenotypes across life-history stages and their influence

on key transitions imply that additional mechanisms, such as enduring physiological or cognitive changes, are probably involved. Moreover, the sibling effect was relatively weak, and a substantial proportion of variation in nestling activity remained unexplained, indicating that innate traits or other environmental factors contribute to the emergence of activity phenotypes. Parental quality represents one plausible factor contributing to these patterns. As high-quality territories are more likely to be held by high-quality parents [62,63], offspring raised in such territories experience a combination of favourable environmental conditions, superior inherited genetic characteristics and improved parental care, potentially shaping activity phenotypes. In addition, parental quality may contribute to the observed sibling effect, as high-quality parents are likely to raise large broods (i.e. two chicks) [63], with both nestlings experiencing conditions that promote higher activity.

The lack of effect of biomass productivity (NDVI) on activity levels, fledging age or movement characteristics at any stage investigated could be interpreted as support for intrinsic behavioural differences. However, it is possible that NDVI represents a poor proxy for the environmental quality of natal territories in golden eagles. Even though NDVI is known as a valid proxy for habitat quality and prey availability in other raptor species, such as lesser kestrels [64], the spatio-temporal diversity of golden eagle prey—including their strong reliance on carcasses during winter—may obscure such a relationship. This is underpinned by the lack of relationship between NDVI and nestling body condition (LMM: estimate: -48.5 , 95% CrI: -183.6 – 86.6). In addition, other environmental factors, such as the topographic configuration of territories (cf. [37,46]), and associated flight conditions or parental quality may be more decisive for food accessibility (parental provisioning), juvenile flight propensity and locomotory development [37,46].

The effect of nest exposure on the timing of fledging corroborates the importance of topography and thermal conditions for behavioural development. Early fledging observed in southern-exposed nests could indicate that southern slopes offer improved flight conditions to parents for provisioning but also to juveniles, allowing them to fledge earlier. It also implies that optimal nest sites are limiting, or thermal conditions need to be traded against other factors affecting nest site selection. Although features indirectly related to thermal conditions have been shown to influence nest-site choice in golden eagles [65] and in other raptors, such as booted eagles (*Hieraaetus pennatus*) and long-legged buzzards (*Buteo rufinus*) [66], the role of thermal conditions in shaping nest-site selection remains understudied. Overall, our results suggest that activity phenotypes probably arise from an interplay of intrinsic, social, environmental and parental factors—but the direct and indirect contributions of these factors warrant further investigation.

4.2. Carry-over of the activity phenotype

There is ample evidence for a strong link between conditions experienced in the nest and post-fledging performance across numerous species [4,19]. Our findings that golden eagle nestlings with high activity levels fledged at a young age and maintained elevated post-fledging activity suggest that this effect is rooted in behavioural differences. In long-lived species with high post-fledging survival, such as golden eagles [67], nestling activity phenotypes seem to carry over to affect the behaviour throughout the entire post-fledging stage. In other species, such as zebra finches (*Taeniopygia guttata*) or red kites (*Milvus milvus*), carry-over effects of nest conditions on behaviour and fitness correlates later in life were often attributed to physiological mechanisms such as oxidative stress, corticosterone levels or telomere length [13,14]. We now show that nest conditions can also affect the nestlings' activity phenotype, and that these behavioural differences can carry over to later life stages, influencing key life-history transitions.

Forays outside the parental territory may be a beneficial move to attenuate the risks of dispersal: forays allow individuals to obtain information on the surrounding environment and gain experience before leaving the parental territory permanently [24]. During forays, juveniles may assess the relative habitat quality of their natal range [68], practise localizing suitable feeding grounds and beneficial flight conditions [69], or learn to avoid agonistic behaviours of conspecific and anthropogenic threats after departure [70]. More active juveniles may thus probably gain fitness benefits from undertaking more forays if the knowledge gain carries over to the dispersal phase.

The subsequent permanent departure from the natal area is a fundamental change point in the life of juvenile animals, as it entails leaving the known environment, the end of parental care and concomitant shelter from predation or conspecific aggression [24]. This life-history transition to natal dispersal is thus risky and should only occur at a point when skills are developed to a degree that allows one to deal with these risks [71]. Juveniles may thus have an interest in staying with their

parents for as long as possible to gain experience, reach behavioural maturity and a good nutritional status [29]. However, pampering their offspring may impose costs on parents that can be reduced by early emigration of juveniles [72]. In addition, a timely emigration possibly also benefits juveniles, as it can support the detection and monopolization of patchy food resources, the acquisition of high-quality floater areas or higher competitive ability in the social system [24,73]. The fact that individuals with high activity levels emigrated early suggests that they reach this point earlier than individuals with low activity levels. This is supported by a strong positive correlation between overall post-fledging activity levels and the increase in activity levels (correlation between random intercept and random slope of ODBA: Pearson's $r = 0.89$). Nonetheless, the reduced certainty of the activity effect on departure timing indicates that departure decisions are multifactorial and characterized by considerable individual variation. Even so, the accumulated differences associated with the high activity phenotype at departure may help reduce dispersal costs to enhance survival [12,71], allow for overcoming energetic constraints of dispersal [31,74] and facilitate an optimal dispersal outcome by increasing the likelihood of finding and settling in high-quality habitats early in life [11]. Similar patterns have been observed in white storks (*Ciconia ciconia*), where pre- and post-fledging activity affected future survival by shaping the fledging to migration period [12]. Thus, the carry-over of activity differences from the nest to the post-fledging period and its subsequent translation to the start of the next life stage may thus ultimately have pursuing effects on post-dispersal stages [11,17].

5. Conclusions

Despite a relatively small sample size, we found evidence for persistent behavioural phenotypes driving two life-history transitions. Although the underlying causes remain inconclusive, activity phenotypes emerging in the nest persisted into the post-fledging period and shaped the timing of key life-history transitions and movement decisions in juvenile golden eagles. Notably, when propagating differences in nestling activity up to emigration, nestlings with the highest activity emigrated on average 18 days earlier than those with the lowest activity. Our study, therefore, adds to the growing body of research demonstrating that behavioural phenotypes arising in early life can persist across stages, representing a potential mechanism linking early-life conditions to future survival and reproduction. Further research is needed to clarify the drivers of these activity phenotypes and identify the behaviours and movement types involved in increased activity levels, which will refine our understanding of the behavioural mechanisms connecting early-life conditions to individual fitness in long-lived animals. Such insights will also allow for better predictions of their population-level consequences. To overcome the statistical limitations arising from behavioural and phenotypic heterogeneity, future studies should be based on larger sample sizes to confirm these patterns and explore their variability across populations and environments.

Ethics. Handling, tagging and marking of golden eagle nestlings in Switzerland were carried out under the permit by the Federal Food Safety and Veterinary Office Grisons (licence no. GR 2017_06, GR 2018_05E, GR 2019_03E). In Italy, the permissions for handling, tagging and marking were obtained from the autonomous region of South Tyrol (Dekret 12257/2018 and Dekret 8788/2020), as well as from the Regione Lombardia and Sondrio Province for ringing and tagging in Lombardia and South Tyrol by ISPRA (Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale) with the Richiesta di autorizzazione alla cattura di fauna selvatica per scopi scientifici (l.r. 26/93). All procedures followed the ASAB/ABS guidelines for the ethical treatment of animals in behavioural research and teaching, and all applicable international, national and/or institutional guidelines for the care and use of animals were followed. The birds were handled with maximum care, and disturbance to nests was kept to a minimum. Ethical approval for involving animals in this study was received through the application procedure for ringing permits and the scientific commission of the Swiss Ornithological Institute.

Data accessibility. Data and code are available on the vogelwarte.ch Open Repository and Archive [75].

Supplementary material is available online [76].

Declaration of AI use. AI-assisted technologies such as DeepL and Microsoft Copilot were used for correcting text fragments and improving the writing style of individual sentences.

Authors' contributions. S.-S.Z.: conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, visualization, writing—original draft; M.U.G.: conceptualization, funding acquisition, investigation, methodology, project administration, resources, supervision, validation, writing—review and editing; J.S.H.: conceptualization, data curation, investigation, methodology, project administration, resources, supervision, validation, writing—review and editing; E.B.: data curation, funding acquisition, project administration, resources, writing—review and editing; K.S.: conceptualization, data curation, funding acquisition, project administration, resources, validation, writing—review and editing; W.F.: data curation, funding acquisition, project administration, resources, writing—review and editing; D.J.: data curation, funding acquisition, project administration, resources, validation, writing—

review and editing; M.T.: conceptualization, formal analysis, funding acquisition, investigation, methodology, project administration, resources, supervision, validation, visualization, writing—review and editing.

All authors gave final approval for publication and agreed to be held accountable for the work performed therein.

Conflict of interest declaration. We declare we have no competing interests.

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References

- Moran NA. 1994 Adaptation and constraint in the complex life cycles of animals. *Annu. Rev. Ecol. Syst.* **25**, 573–600. (doi:10.1146/annurev.es.25.110194.003041)
- Low M, Pärt T. 2009 Patterns of mortality for each life-history stage in a population of the endangered New Zealand stitchbird. *J. Anim. Ecol.* **78**, 761–771. (doi:10.1111/j.1365-2656.2009.01543.x)
- Aykanat T, McLennan D, Metcalfe NB, Prokko JM. 2024 Early survival in Atlantic salmon is associated with parental genotypes at loci linked to timing of maturation. *Evolution* **78**, 1441–1452. (doi:10.1093/evolut/qpae072)
- Naef-Daenzer B, Gruebler MU. 2016 Post-fledging survival of altricial birds: ecological determinants and adaptation. *J. Field Ornithol.* **87**, 227–250. (doi:10.1111/jfo.12157)
- Perrig M, Opped S, Tschumi M, Keil H, Naef-Daenzer B, Gruebler MU. 2024 Juvenile survival of little owls decreases with snow cover. *Ecol. Evol.* **14**, e11379. (doi:10.1002/ece3.11379)
- Nägeli M, Scherler P, Witzcak S, Catitti B, Aebischer A, van Bergen V, Kormann U, Gruebler MU. 2022 Weather and food availability additively affect reproductive output in an expanding raptor population. *Oecologia* **198**, 125–138. (doi:10.1007/s00442-021-05076-6)
- Osorno JL, Drummond H. 2003 Is obligate siblicidal aggression food sensitive? *Behav. Ecol. Sociobiol.* **54**, 547–554. (doi:10.1007/s00265-003-0667-3)
- Moore MP, Martin RA. 2019 On the evolution of carry-over effects. *J. Anim. Ecol.* **88**, 1832–1844. (doi:10.1111/1365-2656.13081)
- Le Galliard JF, Clobert J, Ferrière R. 2004 Physical performance and Darwinian fitness in lizards. *Nature* **432**, 502–505. (doi:10.1038/nature03057)
- Lindström J. 1999 Early development and fitness in birds and mammals. *Trends Ecol. Evol.* **14**, 343–348. (doi:10.1016/s0169-5347(99)01639-0)
- Van de Pol M, Bruinzeel LW, Heg D, Van der Jeugd HP, Verhulst S. 2006 A silver spoon for a golden future: long-term effects of natal origin on fitness prospects of oystercatchers (*Haematopus ostralegus*). *J. Anim. Ecol.* **75**, 616–626. (doi:10.1111/j.1365-2656.2006.01079.x)
- Rotics S *et al.* 2021 Early-life behaviour predicts first-year survival in a long-distance avian migrant. *Proc. R. Soc. B Biol. Sci.* **288**, 20202670. (doi:10.1098/rspb.2020.2670)
- Reichert S, Criscuolo F, Zahn S, Arrivé M, Bize P, Massemin S. 2015 Immediate and delayed effects of growth conditions on ageing parameters in nestling zebra finches. *J. Exp. Biol.* **218**, 491–499. (doi:10.1242/jeb.109942)
- Catitti B, Gruebler MU, Kormann UG, Scherler P, Witzcak S, van Bergen VS, Jenni-Eiermann S. 2022 Hungry or angry? Experimental evidence for the effects of food availability on two measures of stress in developing wild raptor nestlings. *J. Exp. Biol.* **225**, jeb244102. (doi:10.1242/jeb.244102)
- Kasumovic MM. 2013 The multidimensional consequences of the juvenile environment: towards an integrative view of the adult phenotype. *Anim. Behav.* **85**, 1049–1059. (doi:10.1016/j.anbehav.2013.02.009)
- Whiteside MA, Sage R, Madden JR. 2016 Multiple behavioural, morphological and cognitive developmental changes arise from a single alteration to early life spatial environment, resulting in fitness consequences for released pheasants. *R. Soc. Open Sci.* **3**, 160008. (doi:10.1098/rsos.160008)
- Catitti B, Gruebler MU, Farine DR, Kormann UG. 2024 Natal legacies cause social and spatial marginalization during dispersal. *Ecol. Lett.* **27**, e14366. (doi:10.1111/ele.14366)
- Jones TM, Kaiser SA, Sillett TS. 2026 Post-fledging ecology of birds: emergent patterns, knowledge gaps, and future frontiers. *Biol. Rev.* **101**, 237–267. (doi:10.1111/brv.70080)

19. Cornell A, Gibson KF, Williams TD. 2017 Physiological maturity at a critical life-history transition and flight ability at fledging. *Funct. Ecol.* **31**, 662–670. (doi:10.1111/1365-2435.12777)
20. Ruaux G, Lumineau S, de Margerie E. 2020 The development of flight behaviours in birds. *Proc. R. Soc. B Biol. Sci.* **287**, 20200668. (doi:10.1098/rspb.2020.0668)
21. Radersma R, Tinbergen JM, Komdeur J. 2011 Do brood sex ratio, nestling development and sex affect fledging timing and order? An experimental study on great tits. *Anim. Behav.* **81**, 69–75. (doi:10.1016/j.anbehav.2010.09.007)
22. Perrig M, Gruebler MU, Keil H, Naef-Daenzer B. 2014 Experimental food supplementation affects the physical development, behaviour and survival of little owl *Athene noctua* nestlings. *Ibis* **156**, 755–767. (doi:10.1111/ibi.12171)
23. Roff DA, Remes V, Martin TE. 2005 The evolution of fledging age in songbirds. *J. Evol. Biol.* **18**, 1425–1433. (doi:10.1111/j.1420-9101.2005.00958.x)
24. Clobert J, Baguette M, Benton TG, Bullock JM. 2012 *Dispersal ecology and evolution*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
25. Whitfield DP, Fielding AH, Anderson D, Benn S, Dennis R, Grant J, Weston ED. 2022 Age of first territory settlement of golden eagles *Aquila chrysaetos* in a variable competitive landscape. *Front. Ecol. Evol.* **10**, 743598. (doi:10.3389/fevo.2022.743598)
26. Fielding AH, Anderson D, Benn S, Reid R, Tingay R, Weston ED, Whitfield DP. 2023 Substantial variation in prospecting behaviour of young golden eagles *Aquila chrysaetos* defies expectations from potential predictors. *Diversity* **15**, 506. (doi:10.3390/d15040506)
27. Hatzl JS. 2024 Tracking behavioural trajectories: early-life effects on natal dispersal patterns in golden eagles (*Aquila chrysaetos*). PhD thesis, [Zürich, Switzerland]: ETH Zürich. (doi:10.3929/ethz-b-000724279)
28. Hemery A, Mugnier-Lavorel L, Itty C, Duriez O, Besnard A. 2023 Timing of departure from natal areas by golden eagles is not constrained by acquisition of flight skills. *J. Avian Biol.* **2023**, e03111. (doi:10.1111/jav.03111)
29. Weston ED, Whitfield DP, Travis JMJ, Lambin X. 2018 The contribution of flight capability to the post-fledging dependence period of golden eagles. *J. Avian Biol.* **49**, e01265. (doi:10.1111/jav.01265)
30. Fattedert J, Perrig M, Naef-Daenzer B, Gruebler MU. 2019 Experimentally disentangling intrinsic and extrinsic drivers of natal dispersal in a nocturnal raptor. *Proc. R. Soc. B Biol. Sci.* **286**, 20191537. (doi:10.1098/rspb.2019.1537)
31. Robles H, Ciudad C, Porro Z, Fattedert J, Pasinelli G, Tschumi M, Vila M, Gruebler MU. 2022 Phenotypic and environmental correlates of natal dispersal movements in fragmented landscapes. *Landsc. Ecol.* **37**, 2819–2833. (doi:10.1007/s10980-022-01509-6)
32. Wilson RP, White CR, Quintana F, Halsey LG, Liebsch N, Martin GR, Butler PJ. 2006 Moving towards acceleration for estimates of activity-specific metabolic rate in free-living animals: the case of the cormorant. *J. Anim. Ecol.* **75**, 1081–1090. (doi:10.1111/j.1365-2656.2006.01127.x)
33. Brown DD, Kays R, Wikelski M, Wilson R, Klimley A. 2013 Observing the unwatchable through acceleration logging of animal behavior. *Anim. Biotelem.* **1**, 20. (doi:10.1186/2050-3385-1-20)
34. Jenny D, Denis S, Cruickshank SS, Tschumi M, Hatzl J, Haller H. 2024 The golden eagle in Switzerland. In *The golden eagle around the world: a monograph on a holarctic raptor* (eds J Bautista, DE Ellis), pp. 367–394. Surrey, Canada: Hancock House Publishers.
35. Watson J. 2010 *The golden eagle*, 2nd edn. London, UK: Poyser Monographs.
36. Soutullo A, Urios V, Ferrer M, Peñarrubia SG. 2006 Dispersal of golden eagles *Aquila chrysaetos* during their first year of life. *Bird Study* **53**, 258–264. (doi:10.1080/00063650609461441)
37. Nourani E et al. 2024 Developmental stages shape the realized energy landscape for a flight specialist. *Elife* **13**, RP98818. (doi:10.7554/elife.98818.3)
38. Bassi E. 2024 Golden eagles in northern Italy. In *The golden eagle around the world: a monograph on a holarctic raptor* (eds J Bautista, DE Ellis), pp. 345–365. Surrey, Canada: Hancock House Publishers.
39. Kenward RE. 2001 *A manual for wildlife radio tagging*. London, UK: Academic Press.
40. Kranstauber B, Cameron A, Weizerl R, Fountain T, Tilak S, Wikelski M, Kays R. 2011 The movebank data model for animal tracking. *Environ. Model. Softw.* **26**, 834–835. (doi:10.1016/j.envsoft.2010.12.005)
41. Weston ED, Whitfield DP, Travis JMJ, Lambin X. 2013 When do young birds disperse? Tests from studies of golden eagles in Scotland. *BMC Ecol.* **13**, 42. (doi:10.1186/1472-6785-13-42)
42. Baddeley A, Rubak E, Turner R. 2015 *Spatial point patterns: methodology and applications with R*. Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press. (Chapman & Hall/CRC Interdisciplinary Statistics).
43. Scharf A. 2018 moveACC: analysis and handling of acceleration data. R package. See <https://gitlab.com/anneks/moveACC>.
44. Perrig M, Gruebler MU, Keil H, Naef-Daenzer B. 2017 Post-fledging survival of little owls *Athene noctua* in relation to nestling food supply. *Ibis* **159**, 532–540. (doi:10.1111/ibi.12477)
45. Regos A, Arenas-Castro S, Tapia L, Domínguez J, Honrado JP. 2021 Using remotely sensed indicators of primary productivity to improve prioritization of conservation areas for top predators. *Ecol. Indic.* **125**, 107503. (doi:10.1016/j.ecolind.2021.107503)
46. Hemery A, Duriez O, Itty C, Henry PY, Besnard A. 2024 Using juvenile movements as a proxy for adult habitat and space use in long-lived territorial species: a case study on the golden eagle. *J. Avian Biol.* **2024**, 03212. (doi:10.1111/jav.03212)
47. ORNL DAAC. 2018 MODIS and VIIRS land products global subsetting and visualization tool. Oak Ridge, TN: ORNL DAAC. ()
48. QGIS Development Team. 2021 QGIS Geographic Information System. Open source geospatial foundation. See <http://qgis.osgeo.org>.
49. R Core Team. 2020 R: A language and environment for statistical computing. Vienna, Austria: R Foundation for Statistical Computing. See <http://www.r-project.org/>.
50. Goodrich B, Gabry J, Ali I, Brilleman S. 2022 rstanarm: Bayesian applied regression modeling via Stan. See <https://mc-stan.org/rstanarm>.
51. Brooks SP, Gelman A. 1998 General methods for monitoring convergence of iterative simulations. *J. Comput. Graph. Stat.* **7**, 434–455. (doi:10.1080/10618600.1998.10474787)

52. Gabry J. 2018 ShinyStan: interactive visual and numerical diagnostics and posterior analysis for Bayesian models. *R package version 2.5.0*. See <https://mc-stan.org/shinystan/>.
53. Paradis E, Schliep K. 2019 ape 5.0: an environment for modern phylogenetics and evolutionary analyses in R. *Bioinformatics* **35**, 526–528. (doi:10.1093/bioinformatics/bty633)
54. Pebesma EJ, Bivand RS. 2005 Classes and methods for spatial data in R. *R. News*. **5**, 9–13.
55. Williams HJ, Shepard ELC, Durieq O, Lambertucci SA. 2015 Can accelerometry be used to distinguish between flight types in soaring birds? *Anim. Biotelemetry* **3**, 45. (doi:10.1186/s40317-015-0077-0)
56. Ellis DH. 1979 Development of behavior in the golden eagle. *Wildl. Monogr.* **70**, 3–94.
57. Catitti B, Kormann UG, van Bergen VS, Gruebler MU. 2023 Turning tables: food availability shapes dynamic aggressive behaviour among asynchronously hatching siblings in red kites *Milvus milvus*. *R. Soc. Open Sci.* **10**, 230328. (doi:10.1098/rsos.230328)
58. Pigeon G *et al.* 2019 Silver spoon effects are constrained under extreme adult environmental conditions. *Ecology* **100**, 02886. (doi:10.1002/ecy.2886)
59. Houdelier C, Lumineau S, Bertin A, Guibert F, De Margerie E, Augery M, Richard-Yris MA. 2011 Development of fearfulness in birds: genetic factors modulate non-genetic maternal influences. *PLoS One* **6**, e14604. (doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0014604)
60. Sih A, Bell AM, Johnson JC, Ziemba RE. 2004 Behavioral syndromes: an integrative overview. *Q. Rev. Biol.* **79**, 241–277. (doi:10.1086/422893)
61. Peig J, Green AJ. 2009 New perspectives for estimating body condition from mass/length data: the scaled mass index as an alternative method. *Oikos* **118**, 1883–1891. (doi:10.1111/j.1600-0706.2009.17643.x)
62. Ferrer M, Bisson I. 2003 Age and territory-quality effects on fecundity in the Spanish imperial eagle (*Aquila Adalberti*). *Auk* **120**, 180–186. (doi:10.1093/auk/120.1.180)
63. Tschumi M, Schaub M, Arlettaz R. 2014 Territory occupancy and parental quality as proxies for spatial prioritization of conservation areas. *PLoS One* **9**, e97679. (doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0097679)
64. Marcelino J, Silva JP, Gameiro J, Silva A, Rego FC, Moreira F, Catry I. 2020 Extreme events are more likely to affect the breeding success of lesser kestrels than average climate change. *Sci. Rep.* **10**, 7207. (doi:10.1038/s41598-020-64087-0)
65. Squires JR, Olson LE, Wallace ZP, Oakleaf RJ, Kennedy PL. 2020 Resource selection of apex raptors: implications for siting energy development in sagebrush and prairie ecosystems. *Ecosphere* **11**, e03204. (doi:10.1002/ecs2.3204)
66. Segura A, Acevedo P. 2023 Forest raptor nest selection traits in Mediterranean forest (Maamora, North Africa): conservation implications. *Bird Conserv. Int.* **33**, e72. (doi:10.1017/S0959270923000266)
67. McIntyre CL, Collopy MW. 2006 Postfledging dependence period of migratory golden eagles (*Aquila chrysaetos*) in Denali National Park and Preserve, Alaska. *Auk* **123**, 877–884. (doi:10.1093/auk/123.3.877)
68. Engler M, Krone O. 2022 Movement patterns of the white-tailed sea eagle (*Haliaeetus albicilla*): post-fledging behaviour, natal dispersal onset and the role of the natal environment. *Ibis* **164**, 188–201. (doi:10.1111/ibi.12967)
69. Bennetts RE, Kitchens WM. 2000 Factors influencing movement probabilities of a nomadic food specialist: proximate foraging benefits or ultimate gains from exploration? *Oikos* **91**, 459–467. (doi:10.1034/j.1600-0706.2000.910306.x)
70. Cozzi G, Maag N, Börger L, Clutton-Brock TH, Ozgul A. 2018 Socially informed dispersal in a territorial cooperative breeder. *J. Anim. Ecol.* **87**, 838–849. (doi:10.1111/1365-2656.12795)
71. Bonte D *et al.* 2012 Costs of dispersal. *Biol. Rev.* **87**, 290–312. (doi:10.1111/j.1469-185X.2011.00201.x)
72. Stearns SC. 1989 Trade-offs in life-history evolution. *Funct. Ecol.* **3**, 259–268. (doi:10.2307/2389364)
73. Bowler DE, Benton TG. 2005 Causes and consequences of animal dispersal strategies: relating individual behaviour to spatial dynamics. *Biol. Rev. Camb. Philos. Soc.* **80**, 205–225. (doi:10.1017/s1464793104006645)
74. Barbraud C, Johnson AR, Bertault G. 2003 Phenotypic correlates of post-fledging dispersal in a population of greater flamingos: the importance of body condition. *J. Anim. Ecol.* **72**, 246–257. (doi:10.1046/j.1365-2656.2003.00695.x)
75. Zimmermann SS, Gruebler MU, Hatzl JS, Bassi E, Safi K, Fiedler W, Jenny D, Tschumi M. 2025 Data and code for 'Cascading carry-over effects of early activity phenotypes in golden eagles'. Zenodo. (doi:10.5281/zenodo.17936655)
76. Zimmermann SS, Gruebler MU, Hatzl JS, Bassi E, Safi K, Fiedler W *et al.* 2026 Supplementary material from: Cascading carry-over effects of early activity phenotypes in golden eagles. Figshare. (doi:10.6084/m9.figshare.c.8390749)